

The Challenges of Motherhood with Microcephaly in Salvador

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the challenges faced by mothers of children with microcephaly in Salvador, Brazil. Through theoretical and historical data and qualitative interviews with two mothers affected by the condition, it seeks to reflect on the social, psychological, and structural impact of motherhood in the face of a congenital disease. The work discusses social barriers, prejudice, and the absence of inclusive public policies in Brazil, especially during and after the Zika virus epidemic in 2015.

Keywords

Motherhood; Microcephaly; Congenital disease; Social inequality; Brazil.

1. Introduction

Microcephaly is a rare congenital condition that gained national attention in Brazil during the Zika virus epidemic in 2015. Salvador, in the state of Bahia, was one of the most affected cities. This article aims to understand the impacts of this condition on the lives of mothers, exploring the social, emotional, and medical scenarios involved.

2. Theoretical Background

Historically, individuals with disabilities have been marginalized. Microcephaly, like other congenital diseases, carries prejudice and misinformation. This section contextualizes the historical evolution of how such conditions have been treated and how this history influences the current reality of the mothers involved.

3. Methodology

A qualitative interview was conducted with two mothers of children with microcephaly living in Salvador. The interviews consisted of six questions, covering topics from the diagnosis to the process of adapting to the new family reality.

4. Results and Discussion

The reports revealed feelings of fear, sadness, and initial shock. Both mothers were unfamiliar with the condition before the diagnosis and had to reinvent their daily routines. Common themes included the lack of institutional support and the strong prejudice faced. Despite the difficulties, both mothers demonstrated admirable resilience and deep love for their children.

5. Final Considerations

It is urgent to promote greater visibility of these mothers' realities and to combat prejudice against children with microcephaly. The lack of public support, combined with social inequality, worsens the situation faced by these families. This article aims to give voice to these women and encourage more humane and inclusive actions.

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